

IPCC DDC at DKRZ: Annual Report 2024

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1. Summary

The total DDC data volume of the IPCC DDC Reference Data Archives hosted at DKRZ contains 2.0 PBytes: 169 TBytes for AR6 (35 TBytes SR1.5 and 134 TBytes AR6), 1.6 PBytes for AR5, ca. 1 TByte for AR4, and ≤ 10 GBytes for FAR, SAR, and TAR each.

IPCC DDC users downloaded ca. 112 TBytes and 193 000 datasets in 2024 with mean monthly downloads of 16 000 datasets/month and 9 TBytes/month. Due to the deactivation of the ESGF portal download option end of June 2024, the dataset downloads per month in the second half of 2024 dropped to 3 % of the value for the first half of 2024 (8% of the downloaded volume). Because of an increase of downloads of +94 % for datasets and +78 % for volume during the first half of the year compared to the same time period in 2023, the total annual downloads are similar to those in 2023 with 98 % of the dataset download number and 80 % of the download volume of 2023. AR5 data downloads dominate with a share of ca. 90 % of the downloads, 10 % are AR6 data downloads and less than 0.1 % are downloads of SAR, TAR and AR4 datasets. Data download numbers of previous ARs show decreases from 2023 to 2024 by -22 % for AR5, by -94 % for SAR, and by -25 % for TAR, and an increase by +88 % for AR4. AR6 data download volumes continue to increase by +21 %.

The download counts per continent can only be provided for the small portion of data downloaded from the DDC portal, as the regional download information from the ESGF for the first half of 2024 is no longer available. These downloads are dominated by Asian users with 72 %, followed by 11 % downloads from North American and 10 % from Europe, 6 % from Africa and less than 1 % each from South America and Australia. Due to the high portion of data downloaded from the ESGF portal, it can be assumed that this share is lower (in 2023 it was about half) and the regional user downloads are more evenly distributed.

DDC users requested no data for selected areas on storage media in 2024. This mailing service has been phased out in 2024. It is to be replaced by an online download option for regional CMIP6 input data subsets of AR6 in 2025.

2. Evolution of data access

The total downloads in 2024, 193 000 datasets or 112 TBytes, are ca. 98 % of downloads in dataset number and ca. 80 % of the data downloads in 2023 (**Figure 1**). The deactivation of the download option via the ESGF portals end of June 2024 (see section 6) caused dataset downloads in the second half of 2024 to drop to 3 % of the value of the first half of 2024 (8% of the downloaded volume). The comparison between the semi years of 2023 and 2024 show an increase of +94 % for download numbers (+78 % for the download volume) for the first half and a decrease of -94 % (-90 %) for the second half. These are AR5 datasets, which make up 80 % of the total DDC datasets (91 % of the total DDC volume).

The mean monthly data downloads are ca. 9 TBytes/month and ca. 16 000 datasets/month. The values for the first half of 2024 are ca. 16 TBytes/month and ca. 30 000 datasets/month and for the second half (without the ESGF download option) ca. 1 TByte/month and ca. 900 datasets/month. The monthly downloads increased from the beginning of 2024 until the deactivation of the ESGF data download option from ca. 7 TBytes and 10 000 datasets in January towards its maximum monthly value of ca. 28 TBytes and 55 000 datasets in May 2024.

The DDC data archive contains about 50 % of the datasets in DKRZ’s long-term archive. With 90 % of the downloaded datasets, the datasets of the DDC Reference Data Archive are the most popular datasets in DKRZ’s long-term archive.

Figure 1: Total data download counts and volumes per months over the last three years in GBytes from the IPCC DDC reference archive.

3. Geographical distribution of data access

For the IPCC DDC AR5 data, direct data access at the DKRZ and until 06/2024 access via ESGF were supported. Downloads from ESGF during the first half of 2024 dominate the statistics with ca. 90 % of the downloads. Due to the deactivation of the ESGF download option, ESGF file downloads are no longer provided by CMCC. Therefore, the DDC continental download information is based on download shares per continent from the DDC portal only (**Figure 2**), a small share of the downloaded data.

A comparison to 2023 can only be provided for the data download portions downloaded from the DDC portal. Download counts per continent from the DDC portal show no significant changes in user location: 72 % Asians, 10 % Europeans, 11 % North Americans, 6 % Africans and less than 1 % each for South Americans and Australians. About 78 % of the datasets in 2024 were downloaded from Africa, Asia and South America, which can be roughly regarded as developing and economy-in-transition countries. In previous years, the data downloads from the ESGF portal showed a much lower share of downloads from Asian users than the DDC portal, about half in 2023 (see DDC report for 2023). Therefore, a more even regional user distribution can be assumed for the first half of 2024, similar to the user distribution for 2023 with about 40-50 % downloads from developing and economy-in-transition countries.

3.1 Data on storage media

The mailing service of data subsets on storage media was phased out in 2024. No user requested data on storage media. This service will no longer be provided. The AR6 input datasets will be made available for download for regions during 2025 to support users from developing countries with low internet bandwidths.

Figure 2: Number of dataset downloads (download counts) per continent for 2024. For ESGF downloads from January to June no user location was available; the regional download distribution shows only downloads of the small portion of dataset sdownloaded from the DDC portal.

4. Data access by category AR

The monthly download rates in 2024 from the IPCC DDC Reference Data Archive were dominated by AR5 downloads as in the previous years (**Figure 3**; online monthly download statistics¹). The majority of AR5 datasets (ca. 92 %) were downloaded via DKRZ's DDC ESGF data node in the first half of 2024 until the deactivation of this download option end of June 2024 with ca. 94 TBytes. The AR5 dataset downloads for the whole year are ca. 102 TBytes of the total DDC downloads of ca. 112 TBytes. The remaining ca. 10 TBytes or about 10 % of the total downloads in 2024 were AR6 data downloads with less than 0.1 % of the total download volume were SAR, TAR and AR4 datasets.

Trends for the different ARs show decreases for most of the historical data: by -22 % for AR5, by

¹ Online monthly download statistics are available at:

https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR6
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR5
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cersearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR4

-94 % for SAR, and by -25 % for TAR. The AR4 data download volume increased against the trend by +88 % compared to 2023. AR6 data download volumes continue to increase by +21 %.

Figure 3: Total annual data download counts (left) and volumes in GBytes (right) over the last five years for the different DDC reference archives (without FAR).

As CMIP6 input data has been available for several years and the publication of the CMIP7 AR7 Fasttrack datasets is planned for mid 2025, the interest of data users has shifted from CMIP5 to CMIP6. However, for the DDC statistics the deactivation of the AR5 data download option via the ESGF portals is the main reason for the observed trend.

5. Review of user queries

User requests are directed to the DDC Partner DKRZ and for AR5 data partly to the ESGF support. A separation of user requests on IPCC DDC issues is not possible. The joint DDC support infrastructure was set up end of 2021. No requests were forwarded to DKRZ from there. DKRZ forwarded a few requests to the DDC Partners.

In parallel to the regular user support channels, additional requests were sent to individuals at the modelling centers or at the data centers.

6. News and activities

Activities were carried out in three aspects:

1. Finalizing the AR6 Reference Data Archive

2. Preparing for AR7
3. Outreach and contribution to trainings

6.1 Progress on remaining tasks related to the AR6 Reference Data Archive

The planned publication of the AR6 Reference Data Archive through the ESGF portal had to be given up when the download option via the ESGF portals was deactivated mid 2024.

Progress was made on the other two remaining tasks, though the LoA with IPCC has not been signed in 2024 and the funding has not been received:

1. Provision of selected variables for regions:

The data subset were selected and the datasets for the regions were generated. Furthermore, the archival workflow has been agreed and a metadata sample has been inserted into the database. The data archival and curation will be started as soon as the financial support becomes available.

2. Complex Citation pilot using Zenodo and additional references in the metadata:

A couple of Complex Citation object examples have been created in the Zenodo sandbox. The metadata schema is under discussion with CEDA and the RDA Complex Citation WG.

6.2 Preparation for AR7

DKRZ has taken up the TG-Data liaison in the WGCM Infrastructure of the CMIP project after the revision of the WIP's Terms of Reference (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951132>). In preparation of AR7, requirements of the TG-Data recommendations for AR7 are communicated through the WIP and relevant CMIP Task Teams and related projects to CMIP (e.g. Earth System Grid Federation – ESGF, and Rapid Evaluation Framework - REF), including data citation and data documentation aspects. Collaborations with REF and expert groups in data management like the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Complex Citation Working Group have been established. The IPCC use case, which combines the aspects of credit assignment and final data provenance/traceability, has been one of the guiding use cases of the WG (see recommendations: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106602>).

Together with DDC Partners CSIC and CEDA, ideas on tools required to support authors in the provision of FAIR guidelines-related information have been discussed with colleagues of the REF project and the RDA Complex Citation WG. Both groups aim to provide provenance / traceability information and are committed to give credit to data providers. Two tool developments of interest to IPCC have been identified:

1. The core of the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF) should be enabled to provide missing but for IPCC required information in the provenance records.
2. Jupyter notebook is interested to implement Complex Citation.

These ideas and their integration into the AR7 workflows will be investigated in more detail in 2025.

6.3 Outreach and training

DKRZ contributed to the DDC-TSU training material meeting after TG-Data F2F and the related TG-Data Subgroups. The high-level publication of the TG-Data's AR7 FAIR data and software plans was coordinated:

Stockhause M, Huard D, Al Khourdajie A, Gutiérrez JM, Kawamiya M, Klutse NAB, et al. (2024) Implementing FAIR data principles in the IPCC seventh assessment cycle: Lessons learned and future prospects. PLOS Clim 3(12): e0000533. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000533>

The IPCC FAIR approach was presented at the following international meetings:

- EGU 2024: presentation of IPCC FAIR approach (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10821975>) at Open Science and Data Help Desk (<https://bit.ly/DataHelpEGU24>)
- [RDA Complex Citation WG](#) sessions at [22nd](#) and [23rd](#) Plenaries
- AGU 2024: elightning talk “Benefit and limitations of the application of the TRUST principles on the jointly managed IPCC Data Distribution Centre” and discussion with Jupyter notebook developer on implementation of the Complex Citation recommendations esp. in context of the IPCC use case
- ESGF technical meeting: The Complex Citation support in context of IPCC FAIR approach was discussed with ESGF and REF software developer.